

TIME DEPENDENT, ENVIRONMENTALLY ASSISTED DEFORMATION BEHAVIOR OF FIBER REINFORCED CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Time-dependent deformation behavior, in bending, of Ceramic Matrix Composites with varying pO_2 environments and temperatures was investigated. Materials investigated consisted of a chemical vapor infiltrated (CVI) β -SiC matrix reinforced with Nicalon[®] SiC fibers having either a BN or C interphase. From this data activation energies for composite damage was obtained as a function of oxygen partial pressure. Finally Thermo-Gravimetric experiments were conducted to obtain the oxidation kinetics of the two interphases (C and BN). The activation energy for oxidation was correlated to the activation energy for damage evolution.

INTRODUCTION

Many of the most promising ceramic matrix composites have been optimized for high toughness at relatively low temperatures. However, the most promising applications of continuous fiber reinforced composites are at high temperatures, e.g. boilers, turbine combustors and heat exchangers. For these composites high ambient temperature toughness is obtained by coating the fibers with a material that allows weak bonding between the fiber and the matrix. This leads to crack deflection, debonding, crack wake fiber bridging and fiber pull out⁽¹⁾. The long term, high temperature performance of these composites has not been adequately studied. It is expected that time dependent crack growth will control the useful lifetime of these materials at elevated temperatures⁽²⁾.

The microstructure of these materials has been specifically tailored so that crack wake processes lead to a tougher material, therefore, crack wake bridging by the fibers dictates their mechanical behavior. The time-dependent effects on mechanical behavior will only come into consideration at temperatures high enough to lead to stress relaxation of the bridging forces. Thus, at elevated temperatures the time dependent response of the fibers in the bridging zone will greatly influence the slow crack growth. The crack velocity-stress intensity relationship of these composites has been previously investigated and higher crack velocities are observed in Ar with up to 20% oxygen than in pure Ar. Properties of the composite deteriorate with either interphase (C or BN) when oxygen was present in the environment, however the effects on the C interface were more drastic⁽³⁾.

Fiber creep reasonably predicts the correct crack velocity and time dependence in pure Ar, however other factors need to be considered when oxygen is introduced into the environment. In

these environments interphase removal or reaction must also be considered. Recent investigations⁽⁴⁾ addressing the kinetics of C - interphase removal from a SiC/SiC system resulted in a mass gain due to SiO₂ formation. However the interphases present were significantly thinner than the interphases in this investigation and the oxygen partial pressure was much greater. The same investigators also observed a mass loss for thicker interfaces which followed parabolic kinetics in the same environment. The parabolic behavior suggests that the transport of oxygen along the interface region is rate controlling and after a certain time the reaction front will be deprived of oxygen. Other investigators⁽⁵⁾ have observed linear kinetics in an oxidation study of a C interface SiC material. Recent work examines the effect of SiO₂ formation at the interface and at matrix cracks^(4,6) and a model has been developed to explain its effects⁽⁷⁾. If sufficient SiO₂ is formed and the interface is small enough then the interface channel will be pinched off and further reaction prevented. From this brief review of the literature, it is apparent that the effect of pO₂ on the oxidation of the interphase and the mechanical properties of composites is rather complex and depends on many factors. These include sample geometry, interphase layer thickness, pO₂ and temperature. The present work will study the effect of pO₂ and temperature on the time dependent deformation of the composite and compare these results with data taken from an inert environment. The effect of pO₂ on interface reaction is also investigated on the same materials and an attempt made to correlate interface reaction with slow crack growth.

MATERIALS DESCRIPTION AND EXPERIMENTAL

The composite materials consisted of a Nicalon fiber cloth of (0°/90°) weave which was infiltrated with a CVI β -SiC matrix. The interface present was either 0.4 μ m Boron Nitride (BN) or 1 μ m Carbon (C) which was deposited on the fibers before the β -SiC CVI step. The as received composites were 8 ply and 4mm X 13mm X 50mm in dimensions and were fabricated by RCI of Whittier, CA. Single-edge-notched bend bars (SENB) with dimensions 3.5 mm X 5mm X 50mm were prepared from the as received bars. The bars had an a/w ratio of ~ 0.25. These specimens were loaded in four-point bending using a fully articulated SiC bend fixture. All tests were performed inside a sealed mullite tube and a split clamshell furnace⁽⁸⁾.

All tests were conducted under a constant force loading schedule for times up to 1 X 10⁵ seconds giving long term displacement/time data. Temperature of tests varied from 800°C to 1100°C. Samples were tested in pure Ar and in Ar with varying oxygen partial pressures. The specimens were loaded such that the outer fiber stress was ~ 130MPa. Testing continued until a decrease in load was observed. Finally samples that were tested in an oxygen environment were brought up to temperature in pure Ar and the gas mixture was switched over just prior to testing. The gas flow rate through the mullite tube holding the specimen was set to ~ 1.6 x 10⁻¹ m³/s. Time, load, displacement, oxygen partial pressure and temperature data are obtained from each experiment. All the load/displacement data was corrected for the compliance of the SiC four point bend fixture used in the experiments.

The Thermo-Gravimetric Analysis (TGA) samples had dimensions of 4mm X 4mm X 8mm. One of the faces was free from SiC coating while all the other surfaces had a 5 μ m coating. After testing it was noted that only the uncoated surface had reacted. Finally all the rates obtained for each sample was normalized with respect to the area of the cut. Tests were conducted from 800°C to 1100°C in varying oxygen environments for periods up to 12 hours. All studies were performed on a thermogravimetric analyzer⁹. Gas flow was maintained at 1 SCFH throughout the experiment. Before each test the sample was placed in an Al₂O₃ pan in the furnace. The furnace was then sealed and the gas flow was allowed to equilibrate before heat up. The furnace was then ramped up to the required temperature and held for the specified time. Mass change was recorded as a function of time. A sample was also run in pure Ar and this showed little mass change indicating that all mass changes are attributed to reactions requiring oxygen.

⁹ Netzsch Instrument STA409

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DISPLACEMENT/TIME DATA

Figure 1. Corrected Deflection vs Time for BN material at 1000°C in Ar. environment

From the four point bend experimental data, plots of corrected deflection as a function of time were constructed (eg. Fig. 1). In order to analyze this data, a phenomenological approach was adopted. This data was analyzed in terms of the following equation. From the data it is possible to obtain the rate of deflection $\dot{\Delta}$ by differentiating the deflection/time plots.

$$\dot{\Delta} = \dot{\Delta}_0 \exp(-Q/RT) \tag{1}$$

where $\dot{\Delta}_0$ depends on the applied stress. In this case all the samples were subjected to the same outer fiber stress and hence $\dot{\Delta}_0$ is a constant. R is the gas constant and T is temperature. For steady state behavior the rate of deflection should be constant. It should be noted that Eqn. 1 is purely phenomenological. The effect of temperature is expected to show an Arrhenius type of behavior from simple rate theory and hence it has been chosen. When the experimental data was fit to the equation (i.e. plot of $\ln \dot{\Delta}$ vs $1/T$), it was observed that the slope of the curve was constant only when data points were taken at a fixed time. In other words, the 'apparent' activation energy, Q_a , was a function of time. This data is plotted in Figs 2 & 3 for the BN and C interphases. The results are also summarized in table 1.

Figures 2. Activation Energy vs Time in Ar. environment for BN Interphase Material

Figures 3. Activation Energy vs Time in Ar. environment with varying oxygen partial pressures.

For both C and BN interface materials in an Ar atmosphere (Fig. 2) the activation energies (Q_c) were observed to initially increase with time due to transient deformation and at longer times reached a plateau value. The values for Q_c were similar for both ~ 200 KJ/mol. Long transient times ($>3 \times 10^4$ sec) were observed in both cases. The activation energy for Nicalon fiber creep is estimated at 200 KJ/mol⁽⁸⁾ and this value is very similar to Q_c obtained for time dependent deformation in these experiments which suggests that in an inert environment fiber creep controls time dependent deformation, however initially a lower activation energy is observed because steady state bridging has not occurred and transient deformation is predominant at short times.

An environment with 20,000 ppm O_2 was chosen to investigate oxidation effects on both the C and BN material. The Q_c was observed to decrease in all cases when O_2 was present in the environment. For the BN interface material the highest value of Q_c was ~ 50 KJ/mol and a transient time of $>1 \times 10^4$ was observed (Fig. 3). The oxidation effect on the C interface was so rapid that data was acquired for only 600 seconds and then the sample failed (Fig. 3). However it was possible to estimate an activation energy of ~ 45 KJ/mol for C interface material in this environment. The transient time was significantly greater for the BN interface material in this environment. Due to the very short time to failure for the C interface materials at 20000 ppm O_2 , similar tests were conducted with an environment of 5,000 ppm O_2 . The transient time was greater in this environment however the Q_c was calculated to be very similar ~ 45 -50 KJ/mol (Fig. 3). From the above results it was concluded that the Q_c for very dependent deformation for C interface materials in a controlled pO_2 environment was similar to the activation energy for carbon oxidation [$Q_c = 45$ -50 KJ/mol⁽⁹⁾]. The transient time was also observed to decrease with increasing oxygen partial pressure.

Table 1. Summary of SENB Data

Interphase Present	Environment	Estimate for SS Creep Activation Energy (KJ/mol)
C	Ar	~ 200 long transient ($>3 \times 10^4$ sec)
BN	Ar	~ 200 long transient ($>3 \times 10^4$ sec)
C	Ar (5000 ppm O_2)	~ 40 short transient (4000 sec)
C	Ar (20000 ppm O_2)	~ 40 very short transient (600 sec)
BN	Ar (20000 ppm O_2)	~ 55 longer transient (8000 sec)

Figure 4. SEM Micrograph of C Interphase material at 1100°C with 20,000 ppm O₂

Figure 5. SEM Micrograph of BN Interphase material at 1100°C with 20,000 ppm O₂

SEM micrographs from the fracture surfaces tested in controlled oxygen environment reveal the removal of the interface due to oxidation for the C interface composite (Fig 4). Similar effects were observed at different oxygen partial pressures. For the BN interface material the interface was not removed but was observed to form a reaction product and the amount of reaction product increased with increase in oxygen partial pressure (Fig. 5).

TGA DATA

From the TGA data, plots of weight loss as a function of time were obtained (Fig. 6a & 6b). Then a curve was fitted to the data and differentiating the curve allowed the rate of weight loss to be obtained as a function of time. Then a plot of rate of weight loss vs temperature was constructed and activation energy determined. From Fig. 7 the activation energy for weight loss for the C interface material was observed to be constant at ~ 45 KJ/mol. This is similar to the peak activation energy obtained for time dependent deformation in the SENB for the C interface materials.

Figures 6a. Weight Loss vs Time for BN interphase material in an Ar. env. with 20,000 ppm O₂

Figures 6b. Weight Loss vs Time for C interphase material in an Ar. env. with 20,000 ppm O₂

For the BN interface material the activation energy for weight loss was observed to increase with increasing time. Also it was noted that the activation energy for weight loss is greater than that for time dependent deformation and this may be attributed to interface reaction pinching off due to reaction product formation along the interface channel. The differences between the activation energies for time dependent deformation and TGA data experiments may be partially explained by considering the following. For time dependent deformation multiple paths are available for oxygen to react with the interface. Also new surfaces are continuously being exposed for reaction. For the TGA samples a single reaction front exists and since a reaction product results the rate of oxygen ingress along the interface channel is greatly hindered. This point is clearly illustrated in the micrographs shown in Fig. 8 & 9. Fig. 8 is from the SENB sample and multiple cracks and reaction fronts at the interface are evident. The TGA sample is shown in Fig. 9 with a single reaction front.

Figure 7. Activation Energy vs Time for both BN and C interphase materials at 20,000 ppm O₂

Figure 8. SENB sample showing multiple paths for oxygen ingress.

Figure 9. TGA sample showing a single reaction front

CONCLUSIONS

In both C and BN interface continuous fiber composite materials the activation energy observed for time dependent deformation is similar to the activation energy for Nicalon fiber creep when samples were tested in an inert environment. This suggests time dependent deformation is controlled by fiber creep in this environment. In oxidizing environments the activation energy for time dependent deformation decreases for both materials however the decrease is greater for the C interface material. Larger transient times are observed for the BN material in oxidizing environments. It was also concluded that the activation energies for time dependent deformation and weight loss are similar to the activation energy for carbon oxidation in the C interface material suggesting that interface oxidation controls time dependent deformation in oxidizing environments. For the BN interphase, the activation energy for time dependent deformation was lower than the activation energy for interphase oxidation. Microstructural examination suggests that the difference is due to pinching off of the single reaction front (due to non-volatile reaction product formation) in the thermogravimetric experiments.

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